

The Properties, Processes, and Perspectives Inter-Framework (P3IF)

Multiplexing interdisciplinary requirements frameworks to manage information risk and foster cognitive security

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Abstract

Requirements engineering frameworks have historically been developed in the context of cybersecurity and have tended to focus almost exclusively on the technical and operational aspects of data security. Now, however, frameworks are being stretched to support interdisciplinary and multiorganizational information systems, requirements, and risks, securing downstream processes such as data analytics and balancing cross-domain priorities and perspectives. In this paper, we (i) explore the purpose of frameworks and their function in facilitating requirements engineering in information systems, (ii) perform an analysis of the relationships and lineages of common frameworks in professional use today, and (iii) propose the Properties, Processes, and Perspectives Inter-Framework (P3IF). P3IF enables flexible requirements engineering for complex information systems by providing a modular abstraction layer between existing frameworks, extending their value without replacing them. Factors from frameworks used across disparate domains are multiplexed to harmonize vocabularies and narratives across different organizations and needs, to create new approaches to managing information risk, and to enhance the cognitive security of decisions-makers by expanding security considerations beyond cybersecurity to include the entire information pipeline from sourcing to semantics.

Keywords: Requirements Engineering, Cybersecurity, Cognitive Security, Health Security, Evidence-Based Decision-Making, Interdisciplinary Interoperable Frameworks, Shared Risk Management, Knowledge Management

Introduction

Institutions and organizations that deal with complex systems and evidence-based decisions ultimately rely on people to process critical information, and this can challenge any individual's cognitive capacity. Where high-consequence decisions are made, this represents an emerging vulnerability. The complex area of health security offers examples of these challenges, and this paper will draw multiple examples from that domain to illustrate an approach toward protecting the integrity and validity of those decisions.

The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) defines evidence-based decision-making as the process for making decisions about a program, practice, or policy that is grounded in the best available research evidence. But what happens when the volume and technical complexity of that research exceeds the situational capabilities of an individual human decision maker? The decision maker then becomes vulnerable to altered evidence, cherry-picked results, misapplied statistics, or unwarranted conclusions. Combined, these might be either innocently misleading or intentionally leveraged into a manipulated scientific narrative that appears technically sound, but is instead dangerously deceptive.

The concept of "cognitive security" arises in response to these vulnerabilities at the interface of human cognitive capacities and organizational information needs. Where the decision maker is a traditional cybersecurity professional, decisions might be made more reliable by incorporating available external affordances, such as expanded cyber toolkits, novel sensors, additional people, and even artificial intelligence, to help guide individual and group decisions in relation to the complexity of the environment. That is, cognitive vulnerabilities might be mitigated by offloading some of the cognitive load through externalization within the environment, a phenomenon sometimes referred to as "situated cognition" [1]. However, with today's massively distributed information networks affecting all facets of society, the functional interaction surface between any organization and the rest of the world has become equivalent to its attack and accident surface, creating an urgent need to support human cognition across all domains, well beyond those traditionally grouped as cybersecurity. We need to focus on the broader domain of cognitive security and adapt yesterday's cybersecurity tools for use by a broad range of organizational actors, while maintaining continuity and the best insights of prior models.

We expand the notion of cognitive security beyond its cybersecurity roots to encompass evidence-based decision-making scenarios of all kinds and in any organization, but especially those which are high-consequence and rely on evidence supplied from interdisciplinary information systems, such as food, water, and health security decisions.

We asked: how might cognitive security be institutionalized and standardized so that it can be integrated with all such evidence-based decisions? It's not a question of securing the scientific or empirical "truth" from the evidence, an endeavor which will always be imperfect. Instead, cognitive security deals with questions and measurements of the integrity of the information supply chain that feeds and expresses organizational decisions, and the validity of the evidence applied in such complex and technical decisions. Cognitive security seeks to protect the integrity of decision-making and reduce the potential for a variety of malignant or negligent influences.

The health security context illustrates the cognitive security challenges that arise in highly complex domains where decisions are made across a broadly distributed system of loosely coupled humans. How can organizations involved in securing healthcare assure the quality of the information flows that inform human decision-making and which all together constitute organizational policy? Securing the integrity of those decisions constitutes a fundamental tenet of health security, but what determines the validity of information in healthcare looks very different to health professionals than it does to cyber professionals.

Health professionals consider evidence to be trustworthy and actionable when the original data arise from large randomized controlled clinical trials, ideally assembled from multiple institutions and contexts and including a cross-section of patients from multiple demographics. Thereafter, the data are expected to have been analyzed by experts in the field, often in combination with other results from similar studies, until the conclusions drawn from the evidence appear to be settled. The results must then be disseminated through peer-reviewed publications and presentations, a process which provides something of a "stamp of approval" on the data and its interpretation, indicating that healthcare professionals are generally able to rely on the findings for their clinical and public health decision-making. And finally, when the evidence has been successfully used for some time, those decisions often become formalized into clinical guidelines.

The requirements to address and measure cognitive security across the multiple steps of healthcare decision-making and its information supply chain need to include a variety of factors beyond those applied in traditional cyber- and data-security analyses. It may not be immediately obvious to professionals working in either evidence-based medicine or cybersecurity how the relevant variables from one domain might be useful to mitigate risk and leverage information in the other domain, and there are no pathways or vehicles to facilitate the discovery of such connections.

The manifest difference between how healthcare and cybersecurity professionals have traditionally appraised and enforced information validity and security requires a thoughtful

exploration of requirements engineering beyond cyber and data security. How might the benefits of otherwise isolated frameworks be leveraged for maximum positive impact across domains? The health security domain represents just one category of information systems that could benefit from enhanced requirements engineering and measurements for information integrity and cognitive security. The information supply chains of many domains include numerous processes and gatekeeping functions that are not represented in traditional cybersecurity information supply chain analyses.

Although the examples in this paper highlight the larger problems of information risk and cognitive security within the medical and public health domains, we note that the absence of far-reaching interdisciplinary collaboration, trust, and shared risk around information systems for organizational decision making, as well as around the information supply chains that support such systems, is a generalized problem across numerous domains and is an increasingly common requirement for risk management. Unfortunately, the requirements engineering frameworks in use today are either too narrow or too broad. They are optimized for singular contexts with domain-specific objectives (such as the pipelines which support decision-making in evidence-based medicine), or they suffer from a combinatorial explosion from too many considerations, which consequently impedes their practical application.

We need to bridge the information and decision security silos. What is needed is a practical method for multiplexing interdisciplinary requirements frameworks to manage cognitive security and protect the integrity of high-consequence, high-complexity evidence-based decisions. If we can make requirements engineering and decision-making frameworks more conceptually “interoperable,” it will help organizations access the benefits of additional decision-making frameworks. This would foster enhanced integrity from those additional frameworks’ information supply chain security requirements, helping everyone to shift toward greater cognitive security. For that we require a deep understanding of existing frameworks and their patterns.

In this paper, we (i) explore the form and function of frameworks in facilitating requirements engineering in information systems, (ii) perform an analysis of common frameworks found in professional requirements engineering contexts, (iii) generalize features of these frameworks to common dimensions, and (iv) propose the P3IF (Properties, Processes, and Perspectives Inter-Framework) for facilitating requirements engineering in emerging complex and cross-domain information systems. The P3IF is designed with an eye toward interdisciplinary, interorganizational, and interoperable information systems, and is intended to extend the value of existing frameworks rather than replace them.

The Form and Function of Frameworks

When faced with requirements engineering for novel complex domains, we often turn to tools such as models, visualizations, checklists, and standards, all referred to herein as *frameworks*, to ensure compliance and facilitate work and communication. Frameworks serve multiple functions in their facilitatory role, helping to:

1. reduce the likelihood of preventable error [2],
2. reduce guesswork [3],
3. facilitate education,
4. enhance situational awareness and sensemaking about a system,
5. aid in identification of needs and requirements of interest,
6. increase the reusability of work given reliable definition of common patterns [4,5],
7. enable formal and visual comparison of complex objects, components, and outcomes, and
8. establish common vocabularies and narratives among practitioners and teams [6,7].

Frameworks often function as a kind of “pre-flight safety checklist,” to ensure that certain things have been addressed before work begins or before work is considered complete, [5] and as a tool to help taxonomize risks, approaches, phenomena, and objects [4,8–13]. Requirements engineering frameworks bring rigor, repeatability, and comparability to otherwise complex processes, transforming implicit heuristics into formal patterns, and, in some cases, formal patterns into accountability and compliance. Where enforceability and compliance requirements are established and in place, frameworks can constitute “duties of care,” rendering the performance of activities more consistent, interoperable, professional, insurable, and trustworthy.

In order to support these benefits, a framework must have some level of accuracy in mapping the system of interest that the user is navigating, but it is also important to consider the tradeoffs between navigability (i.e. usability) and unyielding accuracy. A “1:1” matching of the details of a framework with its subject system does little to reduce the cognitive load associated with decision-making. Don Norman observed that mental models “need not be technically accurate (and usually are not), but they must be functional” [14], which is a practice-oriented analog to the statistician’s maxim that “all models are wrong but some are useful” [15]. The same might be said of frameworks for information systems. The imperative of frameworks is not to capture every minute aspect of the system of interest through overelaboration, but instead to generate economical and evocative models to facilitate the identification of salient relationships (Occam’s razor) and cultivate clarity for what is relevant for a system [15]. Frameworks are maps, not the territories they

represent; they facilitate navigation of the territory and must be updated when it changes, although the mechanisms for framework modification are often informal and decentralized.

Framework expansion and integration efforts have been attempted before, but were frequently approached from within a domain-specific silo or its immediately adjacent neighbors. While requirements engineering frameworks for information management and similar enterprise systems, such as the CIA Triad [16] and McCumber Cube [4], have been repeatedly reinterpreted and revised to account for new challenges, they may not be comprehensive enough to address the rapidly changing landscape of information threats and vulnerabilities. They also may not be enough to serve the needs of cognitive security for a large, growing population of individual decision makers in myriad domains stretching well beyond cybersecurity professionals. The collective migration of nearly all human and institutional interactions onto networked information systems has created an urgent need for information integrity tools, such as frameworks, to be made more broadly available and interoperable. Further, given the roots of these frameworks in technical aspects related to data security, they may not be readily amenable to the inclusion of increasingly important non-technical factors that arise in the expanded set of information systems, such as the many criteria relied upon by medical professionals regarding what constitutes valid evidence for clinical decisions.

Recent years have witnessed emergence of increasingly decentralized data streaming microservices (i.e., the API economy [17]), new statistical and predictive analytics techniques, and expansive computational capabilities. Information systems and decision making have become more distributed and democratized, often requiring individuals to evaluate and act on information without having access to that information's provenance or to the frameworks and other tools which might help assess and secure its validity. This increased accessibility of large scale information repositories and intelligence fusion methodologies have allowed for the rapid development of new interdisciplinary and interorganizational tools, APIs, and knowledge bases, creating new vulnerabilities, risks, and requirements [17].

Existing requirements engineering frameworks were designed during a time of discrete disciplines and single-enterprise focused systems. The information risk issues that arise from interorganizational data sharing, human-machine interactions, information fusion, transformation, and provenance now all need to be considered as a baseline for operations across a variety of domains and as being performed by a variety of humans with varying training, backgrounds, and expertise. In addition, new governmental and self-regulatory compliance regimes, such as ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance), as well as previously

fringe requirements such as the energy efficiency of computer algorithms, are now becoming more commonplace considerations. **Decision-making and information environments have become inseparable.**

It is increasingly clear that common frameworks for information systems in professional use today were not designed to enable accounting for such factors without bending their interpretation well beyond their commonsense use [16] or creating new communication challenges [18,19], especially when the factors of interest move outside the specific domain of data security into that of emerging cognitive security. Organizations now need to consider integrity and security not just in relation to data, but also in relation to data sourcing, collection, analysis, modeling, interaction context, and decision making itself. As overall human and organizational interaction volumes continue their exponential growth, alongside the derivative novelty and complexity that such growth causes, the benefits of transitioning from heuristics to evidence-based design and requirements engineering is needed across a variety of domains.

Despite the availability of many relevant guidelines, standards, and frameworks [3,13,20], guidance as to what constitutes an optimal “fit”, at a strategic level, among a new or complex system’s components, mechanisms, context, and intended functions, remains relatively obscure and ephemeral, even with integration of analytical and quantitative tools. After all, it is often the case that the only indication that a more optimal system might exist is the logical implication borne from errors or “mis-fits” between the system and its intended function. That is, if there is a system which currently demonstrates poor fit for purpose, then the implication is that another one might exist that does not [21,22]. In situations where a domain’s nascency, subjectivity, complexity, or rate of change prevents functional or stable reduction of its systems into manageable parts and areas of concern, optimal fit must be achieved through operational art (i.e., creative and opportunistic decision-making) [5].

Frameworks for Information Systems

Common frameworks, such as the cybersecurity CIA Triad, have undergone significant elaborations and transformations over time to account for changes to the environments in which they are applied [13,16]. An emergent pattern within this family of frameworks is the juxtaposition of potential requirements categories through the use of matrices and overlays, leveraging combinatorics to display a much larger number of relevant factors (see Figure 1). Given complex, continuous, and rapid change, pressure on performance within the information environment, and such frameworks’ roots in technical and operational aspects of data security, it is possible that inclusion of newly relevant factors has led to an

combinatorial explosion of factors and an overcomplication of frameworks which can create internal inconsistencies and hinder their functional utility (see Figure 1F and Figure 2). Further, it has led to frameworks which confuse the map with the territory; that is, the attempt to capture all relevant factors can inadvertently encourage a framework to be applied as a “blueprint” for its respective system, a function for which abstract frameworks are neither designed nor well-suited.

Figure 1. Representation of the expansion of frameworks over time (A) Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability Triad (CIA) [23], (B) Parkerian Hexad (PHEXAD) [23], (C) McCumber Cube (MCS) [3], (D) Maconachy, Schou, Ragsdale Model (MSR) [18], (E) Information Assurance cube (IAC) [13], (F) Expanded MSR Cube (MSR_Expanded) [18],

Figure 2. A representation of an apparent inconsistency in the documentation of the Federal Enterprise Architecture Framework adapted from [19]. Here, 6 sub-architecture domains are listed in the documentation, but the sixth, "security", does not appear to be a part of the same category with the other 5 listed domains in the visual model.

Multi-Organization Information Systems

We live in an age where interdisciplinary multi-organizational interdependencies affect the reliability of information and interacting systems across a variety of domains. The extensive touchpoints across disciplines and organizations which represent those interdependencies afford organizations opportunities for cross-fertilization and shared risk, but at the same time expose those organizations to vulnerabilities of misunderstanding and attack. Frameworks which have been applied over the previous decades in these fields reflect a time when analysis and understanding of information systems was constrained within discrete disciplines and featured a single-organization focus (i.e., single *enterprise* focus). These bounded approaches are rendered anachronistic, and less “fit for function” in today’s setting due to the realities associated with developments across the API economy and platform integrations, advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI), new methods of statistical and predictive analytics, and the interorganizational and distributed nature of risk (e.g., food security, public health, or information ecosystems). Sustainable and resilient information management systems now require a variety of interconnected properties and processes, and each of those from a variety of perspectives, within a context of continuous change. Unfortunately, system designers often have little access to training, education, or experience with such additional factors.

An expansive number of variables have become relevant for multi-organization information systems, not just in the interest of usability and system quality, but also for the purpose of risk management and liability reduction in increasingly networked domains and emerging regulatory requirements [24–27]. These and other similar factors have been summarized elsewhere as Business, Operations, Legal, Technical, and Social (BOLTS) functions [28,29]. Common frameworks appear unable to account for such factors without substantially bending their interpretation [16] or expanding their scope to address these factors to the point of overburdening the frameworks’ navigability [18,19].

Methodology

Here we perform a literature analysis and synthesis exploring the history, form, and function of a set of common professional requirements engineering frameworks for organizational decision making and supporting information systems. We present and summarize these frameworks’ properties and evolution, and explore how we might integrate such diverse frameworks without falling into the common trap of adding new standards [30] to replace the old. This line of inquiry will result in the introduction of the

“Properties, Processes, and Perspectives Inter-Framework” (P3IF), an integrating abstraction layer that is described in later sections of the paper.

Our analysis is intended to derive common patterns [10,11,31] from among existing frameworks for information systems, with a particular focus on combinatorial frameworks (i.e., those which use matrices and overlays to enable more efficient navigation of multiple requirements). Our approach for exploring pathways of interoperability among frameworks is to use the derived patterns as indicators that sets of existing frameworks might be harmonically coupled. We therefore infer they might be combined in a way that improves multi-disciplinary situational awareness and management effectiveness across complementary dimensions in ways that no single framework can provide in isolation.

Framework Discovery and Collection

First a front-end user interface (UI) and an underlying knowledge management system was developed using the low-code data management platform Coda.io to facilitate collection (Figure 3).

A collection of requirements frameworks was identified and characterized. An exploratory, literature-based “snowballing” method was employed to capture the most relevant combinatorial frameworks for information systems, based upon citations and in-text mentions. The initial scope of search was initiated using widely recognized and used frameworks such as the CIA triad [16], McCumber Cube [3], Department of Defense Architecture Framework (DoDAF) [32], and several others. From that initial set, we engaged in extensive manual citation tracking to identify frameworks that were both antecedent to and derived from those encountered in the review. Our goal was understanding the evolution and influence of these frameworks for information systems. We captured bibliographic details of publications where possible, and stored visual and textual aspects of each framework using the Coda.io knowledge management system. As of the writing of this paper (August 2023), we have included 41 frameworks for analysis. Full names, shortened acronyms, and citations for each framework are provided in Table 1.

Row from View of Q_Models

McCumber Cube COMBINATORIAL YEAR 1991

SHORTNAME: SRC_DESCRIPTION:

ANALYSIS GROUP(S):

PARENTS:

Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability Triad

CHILDREN:

Maconachy, Schou, Ragsdale Model

Information Assurance cube

Modified McCumber Cube

Services Oriented Architecture Security Cube

User Centric McCumber Cube

DIMENSIONS:

Search

- Critical Information Characteristics**
Property
- Security Measures**
Perspective
- Information States**
Process
- + ⋮

Critical Information Characteristics

ATTRIBUTES

Name	PPP
Confidentiality	<input type="text" value="Property"/>
Integrity	<input type="text" value="Property"/>
Availability	<input type="text" value="Property"/>
+	

Figure 3. View of the developed user interface [33].

Common Name	Abbreviation	Sources	Year
Active Inference Conflict Model	AIC	[34]	2021
Archimate	Archimate	[35]	2002
Bell-LaPadula Model	BELL	[13]	1973
Business Process Analysis	BPA	[13]	1980
Business, Operations, Legal, Technical, And Social Framework	BOLTS	[29]	2020
Clausewitz Trinity	CWT	[34,36]	1832
Confidentiality, Accessibility, Integrity, and Safety Pyramid	CIAS	[37,38]	2016
Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability Triad	CIA	[23]	1988
COSO Enterprise Risk Management Framework	ERM	[39]	2013
Cyber Defense Matrix	CDM	[40–42]	2016
Cyber Defense Matrix Reloaded	CDM-R	[41]	2019
Department of Defense Architecture Framework	DODAF	[43]	2003
Digital Enterprise Architecture Reference Cube	DEARC	[44]	2018
Expanded MSR Cube	MSR_Expanded	[18]	2023
Federal Enterprise Architecture Framework	FEAF	[19]	2012
Federal Enterprise Architecture Framework (Early Versions)	FEAF-Early	[45]	1999
Information Assurance cube	IAC	[13]	2016
Integrated Architecture Framework	IAF	[46,47]	1994
Maconachy, Schou, Ragsdale Model	MSR	[18,48]	2001
McCumber Cube	MCS	[3,48]	1991
Ministry of Defence Architecture Framework	MODAF	[49,50]	2005
Modified McCumber Cube	MC_Modified	[4]	2019
Multilevel Model of Enterprise Architecture Modeling	MLM	[51]	2023
NATO Architecture Framework 2018	NAF	[52]	2007
NIST Cybersecurity Framework	NIST-CF	[40]	2014
Observe Orient Decide Act Loop	OODA	[34]	1976
Ostrom’s Knowledge Commons Principles	OSTROM	[34]	2011
Parkerian Hexad	PHEXAD	[23]	1998
Revised CIA	Rev_CIA	[16]	2014
Rumsfeld Matrix	RUMSFELD	[34]	2002
Service Oriented Architecture - Reference Architecture Model	SOA R	[53]	2009
Services Oriented Architecture Security Cube	SOA C	[54]	2012
Technical Architecture Framework for Information Management	TAFIM	[55]	1986
The C4ISR Architecture Framework	C4ISR	[45]	1996
The Clark-Wilson Model for Financial Integrity	CWM	[13]	1987
The Cyber Kill Chain framework	KILLCHAIN	[41]	2011
The Open Group Architecture Framework	TOGAF	[56]	1995
Treasury Enterprise Architecture Framework	TEAF	[57]	2000
Treasury Information System Architecture Framework	TISAF	[45]	1997
User Centric McCumber Cube	MC_UserCentric	[58]	2021
Zachman Framework	Zachman	[59,60]	1987

Table 1. The 41 frameworks collected during literature analysis. Each row corresponds to a framework included, along with an abbreviated name, citation/link, and the year of first reference or of described year of origin. Combinatorial Frameworks (e.g., cubes and matrices), are bolded.

Framework Annotation

Collected frameworks were annotated with key aspects and categorizations following the structure presented textually and graphically within each respective source.

Year

The earliest reference to or the described year of origin of each framework within included texts was cataloged for the purpose of visualizing the relationships among frameworks across time.

Combinatorial / Non-Combinatorial

Combinatorial frameworks were demarcated from non-combinatorial frameworks, reference architecture systems, and other methodologies and approaches.

Image

Combinatorial frameworks were annotated with visualizations found during review.

Dimensions

The dimensions and discrete collections of overlays within combinatorial frameworks were labeled (e.g. 1 dimension for a list, 2 dimensions for a table, 3 dimensions for a cube, and so on), and where no name was found within the literature, given a namespace. In addition, each dimension was annotated as being a collection of properties, processes, or perspectives, after initial collection revealed that all dimensions fell into one of these 3 categorizations.

Attributes

The individual attributes of each dimension were cataloged and named. The underlying data structure was amended to treat attributes as distinct objects, to facilitate common reference in cases where framework derivations or syntheses included the same attributes (e.g. PHEXAD, CIA, CIAS, Rev_CIA, IAC, MC_UserCentric, MCS, MC_Modified, SOA C, MSR, and MSR_Expanded all share the attribute "Confidentiality").

Influences

Where one framework was found to be combined or synthesized with, considered in the development of, or was otherwise an influence on another framework, or where the

working group behind one framework was described as supporting, informing, or otherwise influencing the working group behind another framework in development, the relationship was cataloged in order to enable visualization of genealogies and relationships among frameworks across time.

Analysis Group

After early review revealed common areas in which frameworks were being applied and their common roots, each framework was annotated as belonging to one or more of the following categories (Table 2), based on the contexts in which the frameworks were used and developed.

Category	Frameworks
Defense Systems Engineering	BELL, TAFIM, C4ISR, NAF, MODAF, DODAF
Enterprise Requirements Engineering	SOA C, DEARC, Archimate, FEAf-Early, FEAf, SOA R, Zachman, IAF, MLM, TOGAF
Government Requirements Engineering	TEAF, TISAF, FEAf-Early, FEAf
Finance, Accounting, and Banking	ERM, CWM, BPA, TEAF, TISAF
Data/Cyber Security	IAC, Rev_CIA, CIAS, CIA, NIST-CF, CDM, CDM-R, KILLCHAIN, PHEXAD, MC_UserCentric, MC, MC_Modified, MSR, MSR_Expanded, SOA C
Military Science	AIC, OODA, CWT, RUMSFELD
Interorganizational Collaboration	AIC, OSTROM, BOLTS

Table 2. Analysis Groups and the frameworks labeled.

Figure 4. The 41 frameworks, generated over the decades, reflected a diversity of forms and settings.

Framework Analysis

Given the dimensionality and aspects of each framework, we considered the resulting combinatorics and explored the different ways that aspects within each framework could be combined or compared to better understand overlaps, gaps, and unique contributions (Figure 4).

Finally, a detailed lineage of the different frameworks was assembled. Parent and child relationships were identified based on citation histories and direct references, in order to understand the developmental trajectories and intellectual inheritances among them. This lineage information was processed into a phylogenetic-type arrangement, resulting in “clades” of frameworks based on their common characteristics and lineages. This biological metaphor provides a clear visualization of framework evolution over time. In this context, the arrangement could be helpfully described as “phylo-memetic”. Phylo-memetic trees of each analysis group were rendered, showing influence from frameworks outside the clade (shaded dark), frameworks within the clade (shaded white), and frameworks which represent syntheses among clades (shaded gray) (see Figures 5 through 11). Frameworks from earlier than 1985 were rendered to appear in 1985 to enable clear visualization.

Figure 5. Defense Systems Engineering frameworks. BELL, IAC, TISAF, MLM, TOGAF, TAFIM, C4ISR, NAF, MODAF, DODAF, AIC.

Figure 6. Enterprise frameworks. - MC, SOA C, DEARC, Archimate, TEAF, TISAF, FEAFF-Early, FEAFF, SOA R, Zachman, IAF, MLM, TOGAF, TAFIM, C4ISR, DODAF.

Figure 7. Government Requirements Engineering frameworks. TEAF, TISAF, FEAFF-Early, FEAFF, Zachman, C4ISR.

Figure 8. Financial, Accounting, and Banking frameworks - ERM, CWM, IAC, BPA, TEAF, TISAF, FEAF-Early, Zachman, C4ISR. While the ERM framework did appear to be influenced by earlier frameworks within this clade, and by the McCumber cube and its progeny, no evidence of influence could be confirmed.

Figure 9. Military Science frameworks. DODAF, AIC, OODA, CWT, RUMSFELD, OSTROM, BOLTS.

Figure 10. Data and Cybersecurity frameworks. CWM, BELL, IAC, BPA, Rev_CIA, CIAS, CIA, NIST-CF, CDM, CDM-R, KILLCHAIN, PHEXAD, MC_UserCentric, MC, MC_Modified, MSR, MSR_Expanded, SOA C, SOA R.

Figure 11. Interorganizational Collaboration Frameworks. DODAF, AIC, OODA, CWT, RUMSFELD, OSTROM, and BOLTS.

Patterns and Insights

From evaluation of the frameworks collected, in the context of their history and discussion of their origin, structure, and implementation, the following patterns and insights were gleaned:

- Previous attempts at interoperability layers for frameworks tended to focus on generating one-to-one maps between the interoperability layer's components and those of other frameworks and reference architectures as a basis for comparison [61,62]. While this may have been a feasible goal at the time of initial development, the sheer volume of frameworks makes this untenable, and the bilateral matching arrests further integration across multiple frameworks.
- Requirements "Cubes" are a norm across multiple disciplines (reflecting the ambition of expanding their dimensionality from 2 sets of factors (i.e., a matrix) to 3 sets.
- Expansion and adaptation of existing frameworks to fit particular use-cases or contexts is not uncommon, but each derivative release tends to be considered its own, standalone novel framework to replace the previous one. Later frameworks tend to not be "backwards compatible."
- All dimensions and underlying attributes of all examined frameworks fit into one of the following emergent categories: Properties, Processes, or Perspectives (see Table 3).
- As noted in Table 2 above, the following categories, or clades, of common contexts for the development of frameworks emerged during early review: "Defense Systems Engineering", "Enterprise Requirements Engineering", "Government Requirements Engineering", "Finance, Accounting, and Banking", "Data/Cyber Security", "Military Science", and "Interorganizational Collaboration."
- As suggested in prior sections, the more expansive (multi-factor) frameworks tended to be the most difficult to document, due to inconsistencies in documentation, proliferation of variables, and limitations of visualization.
- Some frameworks, such as the Cyber Defense Matrix (CDM), went beyond the presentation of discrete variables to include continuous factors, using gradient overlays to allow users to fine tune the direction of their attention and to communicate prioritization.

- Many frameworks among the (i) Enterprise Requirements Engineering, (ii) Finance, Accounting, and Banking, and (iii) Government Requirements Engineering clades were heavily influenced or even entirely prompted by either compliance vacuums or guidelines generated by regulatory and legislative acts which mandate certain processes and properties and related evaluative criteria¹. The large number of frameworks in this category serves as evidence for the importance of navigability and communication beyond data security and beyond data generally, to include policy, information sourcing, human factors, and others.

Scope and Limitations of Analysis

The work as presented here is not considered an exhaustive compilation or systematic meta-analysis of all available frameworks for information systems, nor of all versions of the frameworks which have been included.

- Mentions of frameworks in the reviewed literature rarely specify the version being referenced, and on some occasions actually predate the releases of the referenced frameworks found in the “snowball” review, possibly due to the proprietary nature of some enterprise frameworks and their development through working groups (e.g., C4ISR and government working groups’ influence on one another and on industry working groups [45]).
- Full literature meta-analysis would have been unwieldy, as not all frameworks are fully available or fully documented in the literature. Future research could add other frameworks into consideration, potentially including proprietary frameworks, and update or correct errors and missing data in our initial analysis.

¹ Regulatory and legislative acts which prompted frameworks include the (i) Federal Information Technology Acquisition Reform Act of 2014 [63], (ii) Clinger Cohen Act of 1996 [64], (iii) Federal Information Security Modernization Act (FISMA) of 2014 [65], (iv) Chief Financial Officers Act of 1990 [66], (v) Privacy Act of 1974 [67], (vi) Paperwork Reduction Act of 1980 [68], (vii) Government Paperwork Elimination Act of 1998 [69], (viii) Information Quality Act of 2000 [70], (ix) Freedom of Information Act (FOIA) of 1967 [71], (x) Confidential Information Protection and Statistical Efficiency Act of 2002 [72], (xi) Digital Accountability and Transparency Act of 2014 [73], (xii) Geospatial Data Act of 2018 [74], (xiii) Foundations for Evidence-Based Policy Making Act [75], (xiv) Open Government Data Act of 2018 [76], (xv) Internet of Things Cybersecurity Improvement Act of 2020 [77], (xvi) IT Modernization Centers of Excellence Program Act of 2020 [78], (xvii) General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of 2016 [79], and (xviii) California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) [80] among others.

- Some frameworks lack clear or consistent public documentation, so variable interpretations were possible (e.g., as to which visualizations are primary representations of the framework as opposed to other derivative or communicative graphics, which phrasings of a term are core to the framework, or what constitutes a dimension or discrete collection of attributes).

The analysis presented here reflects an initial snapshot of a sampling of frameworks, one that is resolved enough to reveal underlying patterns and foundations for the development of the P3IF; it is presented here as a foundation for future work. The database and accompanying UI have been hosted publicly as a “P3IF Framework Library,” allowing for the incremental addition of frameworks via community suggestion and future analyses [33], beyond the 41 frameworks included already (see Table 1).

The Properties, Processes, and Perspectives Inter-Framework (P3IF)

With the above descriptive analysis completed, we sought to develop a synthesis that would i) enable faithful recapitulation of extant frameworks, ii) facilitate interoperability among frameworks, and iii) support user-led composition of novel situationally-relevant frameworks. Here we describe a synthetic approach towards analysis and visualization of information frameworks, resulting in the Properties, Processes, and Perspectives Inter-Framework (P3IF) tool.

The P3IF is a container for information systems requirements visualizations used to facilitate the navigation and taxonomization of requirements, practices, and vulnerabilities. The primary purpose of P3IF is to facilitate requirements setting in information systems which sit at the intersection of a variety of fields, disciplines, and organizations; that is, to multiplex signals from distinct domains into a single channel of consideration. As such, **there is no canonical form of the P3IF, either visually or formally.**

The P3IF aims to enable the composition and decomposition of complex situations in information systems. It builds on the tradition of pattern languages, which allows for flexibility and adaptability in various contexts. In the informational and cognitive environment, this entails understanding and designing how signals are bundled, unbundled, and multiplexed. In contrast to mainstream (cyber)security discourse, which primarily discusses security as a property of systems, P3IF offers an integrated perspective on security as a multi-dimensional space of Processes, Properties, and Perspectives, affording a broader and more flexible view. As noted above, it is recognized that all framework dimensions and attributes can be categorized into one or more of the 3 categories of Properties, Processes, and Perspectives (P3) (see Table 3).

The P3IF treats any given information requirements cube as an abstract, provisional container for attributes and dimensions of interest, capable of being formed with any combination of Properties, Processes, and Perspectives dimensions (see Figure 12). From a linguistics perspective, Properties correspond to adjectives (e.g., integrity, accessibility), Processes correspond to verbs (e.g., collection, dissemination), and Perspectives correspond to noun-based points of view (e.g., viewed from the medical, legal, or business domain). Each such dimension may itself contain a combination of relevant attributes (e.g., any Process attribute can sit atop any Process dimension). The three dimensions of P3IF are general categories into which all existing framework variables can be sorted and resorted, providing an inter-framework – that is, a bridge between frameworks – that enables the potential for multiplexing analytical variables from across existing frameworks into new and contextually relevant synthesized frameworks. These new frameworks are better matched to current information system complexities and challenges, making them potentially more powerful, useful policy and risk management tools.

P3 Dimension	Definition	Example Aspects
Properties	Qualities the system may or should have, or descriptive characteristics of the system (e.g., confidentiality), or objectives. Static qualities of systems to evaluate or engage.	Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability
Processes	Steps, stages, and their linear or non-linear sequencing, or features and functions which the system must offer. Action-oriented elements of the system.	Collection, Processing, Analysis, Modeling, Dissemination
Perspectives	Viewpoints or contexts from a given domain, area of expertise, or department from which framework is derived or to which it is applicable. Environments in which the system operates.	Business, Operations, Legal, Technical, Social, Medical

Table 3. Definition of Properties, Processes, and Perspectives (P3) associated with P3IF.

Figure 12. Abstract representation of four potential constructions of the P3IF, showing examples of (i) 1-dimensional (bottom right, Properties), (ii) 2-dimensional (bottom left, Processes by Perspectives), (iii) 3-dimensional (top left, Processes by Perspectives by Properties), and (iv) 3-dimensional with multiple implementations of the same dimension (top right, Processes by Perspectives by Perspectives)

Parties which need streamlined navigation and communication of large volumes of properties, processes, and perspectives of interest can use the P3IF to simply *hot swap* attributes or whole dimensions of existing frameworks in lieu of documenting and releasing novel frameworks, or challenging the limitations of the visual medium (i.e., trying to visualize too many factors or dimensions at once in hyper-cube form).

P3IF is not intended to replace other frameworks, but rather to serve as an interoperability layer to permit blending of their considerations and extension of their value, ensuring that their insights and nuances can be integrated into a broader and dynamic context without the need for continuous updating and replacement. P3IF provides greater simultaneous access to the multiple perspectives offered by various existing frameworks, thereby enhancing the efficacy of any one standalone risk mitigation framework. P3IF can help users in a given framework silo to discover and apply other neighboring frameworks, and subfactors thereof, which were previously isolated and unavailable. Indeed, P3IF permits frameworks such as the McCumber Cube to remain unencumbered and unchanged by new considerations and adaptations, by enabling it to be provisionally combined through P3IF with other frameworks' factors on a situation-specific basis. The P3IF anticipates and facilitates a user- and context-guided access to more granular views.

The n-dimensional P3 space is referred to as an "information requirements cube" to fit the professional norms of the cyber domain and the expectation of 3-dimensional representations, but the P3IF can be presented in reduced or expanded dimensionality, from a one-dimensional vector to a 4-dimensional hypercube or beyond, depending on the specific needs of a given use-case. Unlike traditional frameworks, the P3IF is optimized for dimensional flexibility, due to its origin in the patterns of P3 found in the other referenced frameworks. This composability enables assembly of novel actionable frameworks, for example by providing a processual and multi-perspective view on the classic CIA properties (Figure 13), or providing a processual view on cross-BOLTS engagements (Figure 14).

Figure 13. This cubic visualization presents the Processes (Sourcing, Data, Analytics) associated with required Properties (Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability) evaluated in terms of relevant Perspectives (Business, Operations, Legal, Technical).

Figure 14. This cubic visualization presents Processes (Sourcing, Data, Analytics) associated evaluated at the intersection of relevant BOLTS Perspectives (Business, Operations, Legal, Technical, Social).

Usage of the P3IF

Our approach utilizes an initial implementation of the P3IF which makes use of each of its features, in the specific context of the impetus for this work and this paper. While this work was motivated by the particular requirements of health security, it reaches beyond those origins and generalizes to address a need for common interorganizational infrastructure shared among government agencies, military service branches, academia, journalists, and the general public, which we can describe here as a “knowledge commons” [25,81]. Our intention was to assist in developing interaction reliability, information provenance, information value liquidity, and enhanced navigability of such infrastructure within the larger information supply chain.

Interorganizational infrastructure might offer a foundation for features such as management of (i) common reference to abstract objects (e.g., a reference to a paper, or a reference to a particular claim within a paper) and (ii) common reference to relationships among abstract objects (e.g., a direct reference within one paper to another paper, or a reference within a news article to a specific press release). Other features can be readily imagined that might help address concerns across large swaths of current security, privacy, liability, risk, trust and related information system risks. With so many variables to address on the pathway toward such a “knowledge commons,” no single existing framework will ever be sufficient to facilitate situational awareness across all of the dimensions needed for reliable navigation of associated requirements, vulnerabilities, risks, and practices. For example, variables that might need be considered could include: (i) diverse stakeholders, (ii) the involvement of government agency CIOs and the unique compliance requirements that accompany them, or (iii) the presence of complex sociotechnical risks such as dual-use research, semantic integrity, or cognitive security.

The components of an example P3IF rendering might apply BOLTS as an initial Perspectives dimension to help manage the cognitive security considerations of the hybrid knowledge commons system described above. The generality of the business, operating, legal, technical and social categories in BOLTS is intended to prompt broad consideration of a variety of existing perspectives on expectations and performance measurements across multiple types of interactions.

With BOLTS as an initial dimension, the P3IF rendering for the knowledge commons continues with the second dimension. Given that the entire information supply chain is of interest, the team might make use of the “intelligence production cycle” as a Processes dimension, as it has been used as a generalized description for information supply chains elsewhere [82]. The knowledge commons will be an emergent phenomenon of the

achievement of high integrity and trustworthy information supply chains. The application of the intelligence production cycle to generally describe information supply chains establishes precedent for its application here, and additionally, it invites scrutiny of the intelligence context as a potential source of patterns for application in the knowledge commons. In this way, the P3IF also functions as a knowledge discovery tool, the interlocking patterns reveal novel potential use cases and create networks for innovation and new solutions to shared challenges.

Finally, as a Properties dimension, the team might “hot swap” components from the CIA triad and its progeny on an ad hoc basis, depending on the particular component of the knowledge commons to which it is being applied. With a diverse potential user base, different “neighborhoods” in the commons network will have different expectations of the properties of the system with which they engage. The analytical stability offered by the application of uniform Perspectives and Processes dimensions allows for the hot swapping of Properties factors, enabling the localization of features to satisfy the expectations of subpopulations of users.

P3IF is a toolbox that enables reconstruction of existing framework tools. This allows the user to retrieve and use the context-relevant sets of tools best suited to their organizational needs. The P3IF acts as a container for a synthesized model derived from existing models, serving as a provisional vehicle for context-guided selection of risk mitigation criteria from among existing models and enabling constitution, rapid adaptation, and revival and reconstitution [13] of information frameworks (i.e., you can recreate any given framework within P3IF by selecting a previously-published combination of dimensions and aspects). As a consequence of its use across different systems, it can also function as a foundation for integration and innovation, supporting and contributing to trade association functions, and facilitating distribution of relevant cognitive security factors across trades and other forms of human organization, i.e., the “knowledge commons.”

P3IF renderings are not static. They are entirely flexible, inviting exploration of new combinations of variables, and even swapping of factors within each category, which can help lead to new discoveries of strategies for information risk mitigation and cognitive security across previously isolated domains. P3IF renderings can be re-rendered for specific collections or itineraries of requirements, without requiring the need for documentation and dissemination of multiple novel frameworks, although a particular rendering might be promoted as such. Unlike the frameworks from which it is derived, P3IF renderings are intended to be dynamically and contextually constituted from existing framework parts. The promotion of any P3IF rendering to a best practice or standard would not subsume or

replace other frameworks from which it is derived, and would not prevent adaptation of new source frameworks in the future.

We close this section with a final example P3IF rendering, designed to illustrate the interplay of Cyber/Data Security and Cognitive Security, across intersections of different dimensions (Figure 15). Each cell in the cube represents a set of evaluative criteria or a checklist to consider. When applied to the healthcare domain, this rendering suggests an entire suite of new considerations are needed to fully ensure the integrity and validity of evidence-based decision-making in medicine and public health. These observations will be explored in more detail in future work.

Figure 15. A P3IF cube that enumerates combinations of system Properties (Usability, Integrity, Compliance, Interoperability, Efficiency), Processes (Sourcing, Data, Analytics, Semantics, Policy), and Perspectives (Business, Operations, Legal, Technical, Social). Cells in the figure are shaded on a continuum ranging from darker (Cyber/Data Security oriented) to lighter (Cognitive Security oriented).

Discussion

In this work, we conducted a review of requirements engineering frameworks for information systems via a “snowballing” literature method. This allowed us to trace the lineage and influence of these frameworks, giving rise to an understanding of their evolution across time, sectors, and use cases. We then annotated and analyzed each framework’s aspects and dimensional structure, organizing them according to a phylo-memetic scheme, elucidating their evolutionary trajectories and intellectual inheritances. This analytic work prepared the foundation for a comprehensive comparative analysis, culminating in the development of the Properties, Processes, and Perspectives Inter-Framework (P3IF). **P3IF enables adaptive multiplexing and rendering of elements and dimensions from existing frameworks while bridging their gaps**, thereby emerging as an adaptable tool ready to accommodate future theoretical insights and practical additions.

Through our analysis, we have clarified that information frameworks have historically served a dual purpose. In some settings they function as visualizations of reference architecture and detailed archival maps, evidenced by the exhaustive combinatorics of the Federal Enterprise Architecture Framework (FEAF) and Expanded MSR Cube. In other settings the frameworks are used as lean or simplified itinerary maps, exemplified by the sparsity of the CIA (Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability) model. Our P3IF approach allows for a clearer demarcation between these two roles. By employing P3IF, we can establish a comprehensive repository of attributes drawn from among existing frameworks that, when tied to an underlying repository, both constitutes the archival map and allows for economic and evocative renderings of its components without overwhelming the viewer.

P3IF renderings constitute specific itinerary maps that are pertinent to a particular project, mission, or designer, allowing for a necessary separation of concerns in communication and navigation without requiring separation of concerns in the underlying regulatory or taxonomic structures. The P3IF approach provides the means to navigate different requirements because itinerary maps can be rendered on demand from a larger archive, enabling a more streamlined and effective use of these complex information structures [29].

This work lies at the intersection of synthetic intelligence, compositional cognitive cartography, and extended framework-enabled cognition. Synthetic intelligence highlights the need to integrate situational awareness from a variety of perspectives, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of the information landscape. This synthetic approach is grounded in the principles of compositional cognitive cartography, borrowing from

category theory and active inference as a means to construct meaningful and navigable cognitive maps [28,83,84]. Furthermore, this work integrates the notion of narrative information management and knowledge hodology, building on insights from cartography, indigenous knowledge systems and pathfinding, and generalized intelligence production and dissemination in order to reduce cognitive overload and collaboratively manage risk across multiple dimensions and perspectives [6,29,85].

We recognize that current models, while useful, lack a mechanism for interoperability and a nuanced weighting system to account for their proliferating aspects and dimensions. To navigate this complexity, we propose pattern and map-guided relationships among models through P3IF by relying on their commonalities – specifically, through the sorting of their dimensions and attributes as Properties, Processes, and Perspectives. Acknowledging that there is no single perfect number of dimensions or aspects, our work promotes re-composability, allowing for dynamic rearrangement and adjustment of models in response to evolving needs and contexts.

Recommendations

- **Businesses, trade associations, and business leagues** which sponsor conferences and educational sessions should consider introducing sessions to explore the use of the P3IF in requirements engineering and related communications.
- **Banks, insurance and secured lending organizations**, and other financial entities which are already well practiced in risk analysis should consider using P3IF renderings to help communicate financial risk mitigation and insurance products to clients, and to provide guidance during financial engineering processes.
- **Law firms and in-house legal counsel** should consider the use of P3IF for analysis, collection, and communication of legal and regulatory compliance factors.
- **Public Health officials and policy makers** can look to P3IF as a mechanism for policy and systems integration across the vast diversity of sectors and industries that collectively contribute to health security. The ability to re-render based on the context of interest allows for easier navigation and communication of requirements without requiring numerous frameworks or mass adoption. P3IF can help contextualize decisions and balance competing requirements while securing the evidential basis for those decisions.

- **Governments and other social and civil society organizations** should look at P3IF as a potential vehicle for intervention and communicating requirements, since it provides a ready mechanism for access to frameworks relied upon by a given sector. Where the dominant frameworks are known for a given potential object of regulatory attention, P3IF provides a shared vocabulary for intervention and interaction, and a foundation for the presentation of alternatives.
- **Academics and research funding agencies** should consider helping to extend the P3IF approach to so-called “wicked problems” in which multiple, disparate complex problems intersect and where convergence among multiple approaches, disciplines, or organizations is required for analysis and addressment, and should consider potential opportunities for synthesis among fields.
- **Organizations involved in design of systems of all kinds** should use P3IF as an opportunity to synthesize and communicate their existing requirements frameworks, for communication to and with clients (e.g., investigation and explanation of priorities and gaps in requirements consideration), and as an opportunity to more effectively adapt popular frameworks to their use cases.
- **Organizations performing requirements engineering between organizations,** should use P3IF to assist in navigating and translating requirements and priorities among organizations.
- **Designers of information and data communications Systems,** should use P3IF to expand their more traditional cyber- and data-security frameworks to include human factors and ergonomics.
- **Readers and interested parties** should interact and contribute with existing frameworks of all kinds on the provisional front end that the authors are hosting at <https://P3IF.com>, in order to help further explore and amend the phylogeny and history of frameworks in design, and further, to help choose useful dimensions and factors to consider in their use cases.

Disclaimer

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